

Impact government policy toward competitiveness of rice commodity in Banten Province

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ABSTRACT

Rice harvested area in Banten Province in 2015 covered an area of 392 849 ha with a production of 2.189 million tons of unhusked rice or the productivity of 5.54 tons of grain/ha. The purpose of this study was: 1) to analyze the competitiveness of rice commodity in the province of Banten, 2) to analyze impact of policy toward rice competitiveness in the province of Banten, Study method used survey methods, with simple random sampling at the farm level and purposive sampling in vendor level, with the number of respondents 120 farmers. Data was analyzed using qualitative and quantitative analysis. Qualitative analysis used descriptive tabulation. Quantitative analysis used the Policy Analysis Matrix. The results of this study are: 1) The value of PCR (Public Cost Ratio) ratio of 0.28 and DRCR (Domestic Resources Cost Ratio) Ratio of 0.26 means that rice commodity has a high competitive and comparative advantage, 2) The increase of 10% tradable input price will increase the PCR value by 1.3% while the value of DRCR will decrease 1.3%. The Private Profitable (PP) will increase slightly 0.91% while Social Profitable (SP) will decrease sharply as much as 183.3%. The decrease of 10% output price will increase PCR 10.13% and will decrease value of DRCR of 1.3%. The PP and SP will decrease as much as 16.3% and 183.3%. Rice commodity has a relatively high competitiveness, so it is need to increase rice productivity in improving competitiveness and the purchase of grain by Agency of Logistics Affairs according to Government Purchasing Price.

Keywords : Competitiveness, rice, farming, Policy Analysis Matrix, Banten

INTRODUCTION

Paddy or rice planting area in 2015 covered an area of 392 849 ha and harvested area of 386 676 ha with a production of 2 188 997 million tons of unhusked rice or the productivity of 5.54 tons of grain/ha (CBS, 2016). Based on the existing harvested area, 128.421 ha (33.2%) are found in Pandeglang District with production 715780 tons (32.7%), followed by Lebak District with harvested area of 102.828 ha and productions of 575942 tons (26.3%), and the third is Serang District with harvested area of 88.611 ha and production of 510

748 tons (23.3%), the fourth in Tangerang District with harvested area of 50 303 ha and production of 290969 tons (13.3%) and the rest the fourth municipality with harvested area 16 513 ha with production of 95557 tons (4.4%).

Competitive advantage is defined as the ability of a commodity to compete in the national/international market financially, while the comparative advantage is the ability of a commodity to compete in the national/international market economically/ socially. Competitive advantage is also called PCR (Private Cost Ratio) and the value must be <1 in order to have competitive advantage, while comparative advantage is also called DRCR (Domestic Resources Cost Ratio) and the value also must be <1 in order to have comparative advantage (Pearson, 2003; Haryono, et al. 2011; Rum, 2010). The lower/smaller the second value mentioned above then the higher the farming competitiveness or more efficient.

From the study of Zakaria WA et al.(2004), in irrigated rice in four districts (Tanggamus, Central Lampung, South Lampung, and East Lampung) in the Rainy Season (RS) 2002/2003 showed that the PCR value = 0.44, meaning rice farming rice fields have a competitive advantage. A value of 0.44 means that to increase the value added output by one unit in private prices requires an additional domestic factor cost of 0.44. While the value of DRCR 0.40 means that irrigated rice farming has a comparative advantage, which means that for every US \$ 1.00 needed to import these commodities needs a domestic cost of US \$ 0.40. If the value of PCR and DRCR <1 means that the commodity has a competitive and comparative advantage or has competitiveness, meaning that it is able to compete in the international market (Pearson et al. 2004; Mantau. 2012). To determine the competitiveness of rice commodities, this research needs to be done. The purpose of the study were: 1) to analyze the competitiveness of rice commodity in the province of Banten, 2) to analyze impact of policy toward rice competitiveness in the province of Banten.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Location and Time of Execution

The assessment was conducted in Banten province. The location of this study was conducted in four districts of main rice production in irrigated fields, namely: 1) Serang District, 2) Tangerang District, 3) Pandeglang District, and 4) Lebak District. The time period study is for a year starting January 2015 - December 2015 based on research of Siagian, et al. (2016).

Implementation Method of Assessment

The method used in this study was the survey method. The survey method was conducted for primary data collection using interview method using structured questioner toward-farmer respondents. The survey was done in the nearest port to retailer to obtain price data of import /export rice parity price, freight cost and price at the retailer level to wholesalers or vendor at province level. From each sample district, one representative sub-district was chosen and each sub-district selected several representative sample villages, with chosen amount of 30 respondents farmer each districts, so totally 120 respondents (Singarimbun and Effendy, 1989). Besides the survey method o collecting secondary data in related institutions was done to obtain supporting data.

Processing and Data Analysis

Data analysis used was qualitative and quantitative analysis. Qualitative analysis was used for descriptive tabulation analysis. Quantitative analysis used Policy Analysis Matrix (PAM) to determine competitive advantage and competitiveness of rice commodity. The PAM approach was based on two sets of commodity budgets that one used the financial/private (market) price and the other using the social/economic price (Pearson, 2003). The general form of PAM is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Policy Analysis Matrix

Revenue	Cost		Profit
	Input tradable	Input domestic	
Private			
A	B	C	$D = A - (B + C)$
Social			
E	F	G	$H = E - (F + G)$
Divergences			
$I = A - E$	$J = B - F$	$K = C - G$	$L = D - H$

Remarks: A = Receipts in private/market/financial prices. B = Tradable (internationally tradable) input costs in private prices. C = Domestic factor costs in private prices. D = Profit in private price = Private gain. E = Revenue in social prices. F = Tradable input costs in social prices. G = Domestic factor costs in social prices. H = Profit in social price = social profit

Source: 1) Pearson (2003). 2) Monke and Pearson (2004) in Haryono (2011). 3) Pearson et al. (2004)

1. Competitive Advantage (PCR) and Comparative (DRCR)

A. Private Cost Ratio (PCR) = $C / (A - B)$: If PCR < 1, then there is a competitive advantage.

B. Domestic Resource Cost Ratio (DRCR) = $G / (E - F)$: If DRC < 1, then there is a comparative advantage (Pearson et al. (2004); Rum (2010); Haryono et al. (2011)).

Analysis of Rice Competitiveness in Banten Province

Based on the enumeration result, the averaged rice productivity in Banten Province at RS 2014/2015 is 5.835 tons per ha. With an average harvest price of IDR 3725 per kg, the revenue is IDR 21.47 million per ha. Total Cost of Production IDR7.14 million per ha to obtain Revenue IDR 14.6 million per ha. Based on analysis of B/C ratio is known value 2.0 at financial price. This means that paddy/rice farming is financially profitable.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Characteristic of Respondents and Farming Patterns

The enumeration results show that the average age of respondents in Banten province is 50.4 years old with a range of 25 - 80 years old. The average of education duration is 6.6 years (equivalent to grade 1 of Junior High School) with a range of 0 - 16 years old. The area of exploited land in Rainy Season (RS) 2014/2015 is averaged 0.69 ha with a range of 0 – 3.0 ha. The average of owned land area is 0.3 ha with a range of 0 - 3.0 ha. Total non-owned land averages 0.39 ha with a range of 0 - 2.25 ha. The general planting pattern is rice - rice - fallow. The dominant varieties cultivated are 60.7% for Ciherang, 12.7%(IR-64), 12.4% (Mekongga), 8.9% (Inpari-27), and 5.6% for another Inpari.

Table 2. Analysis of Rice Farming per Ha on RS 2014/2015 in Banten Province

No.	Type of Input/Output	Volume	Price/unit (IDR)	Value
1	Seeds (kg)			
	a. certified	25	8318	207,950
	b. non certified	10	2996	29,960
2	Fertilizer (kg):			0
	a. Urea	236	1561	368,396
	b. SP-36	86	1343	115,498
	c. KCL	5	760	3,800
	d. ZA	1.5	2375	3563
	e. NPK Ponska	159	1967	312,753
	f. Pupukkandang	52	355	18,460
	g. Organic fertilizer (s) (kg)	255	497	126,735
	h. Organic fertilizer (f) (l)	0.2	41875	8,375
	i. Solid Fertilizer (kg)	0.3	19110	5,733
	j. Liquid Fertilizer (l)	0.7	76541	53,579

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No.	Type of Input/Output	Volume	Price/unit (IDR)	Value
3	Fluid Growing Stimulants (kg)	1.1	8199	9,019
4	Pesticide:			0
	a. Solid (kg)	7.7	12536	96,527
	b. Fluid (l)	2.4	56046	134,510
5	Herbicide:			
	a. Solid (kg)	0.05	168841	8,442
	b. Fluid (l)	0.7	65339	45,737
6	Others:			
	a. Tax of building and land			31,937
	b. Contribution of irrigation Water Fee			5,348
	c. Contribution of Village			1,142
	d. Rent of water pump and others			172,739
6	Cost of Hired Labour:			
	a. Hired labour (Man Day Work)	100	46615.98	4,661,598
	b. Family Labour (Man Day Work)	12	0	0
	c. Wage of Livestock Service	0.1	65000	6,500
	d. Wage of Tractor Service	2.6	275496.1538	716,290
7	Total Cost			7,144,591
8	Revenue	5835	3725	21,735,375
10	Income			14,590,784
11	R/C			3.0
12	B/C			2.0

Source: Processed primary data of 2015.

Explanation: n = 120 respondents.

Shadow Price Determination

Price Shadow Output

The price of output shadow (rice) is determined based on the border price at the nearest port, namely TanjungPeriuk Port. For rice commodity net importer considers the price of shadow which is import parity price, and US \$ currency converted IDR, then minus freight cost from TanjungPeriuk port to

Serang City, and cost of transportation from Serang City to farmer, and processing fee, so as it is obtained social price rice (output) at farmer level. The details are listed in Table 3. From Table 3, it can be explained, that export price of rice on an export port vessel (FOB) during February - May 2015 averaged US \$ 435 per metric ton (Ministry of Trade Report, 2015). The price of rice is added to freight and insurance costs in the mode of sea transportation for the Association of South East Asia Nation (ASEAN) where freight costs are 1.53% and insurance is 0.1951%, because rice imports are mostly from ASEAN countries, especially Thailand and Vietnam (RI Minister of Trade Regulation, 2015), so that the CIF (Cost Insurance Freight) value of US \$ is obtained US\$ 442.5 per tons. With average of IDR exchange rate IDR. 12,800 / 1 US \$, the CIF value was obtained at the domestic price of IDR. 5,664 / kg. The domestic CIF value is added to the port handling fee of IDR. 38.5 / kg for dry bulk (Indonesian Port I, 2015), and transportation and handling costs to traders (from the results of a survey of transport companies in Serang), and costs rice import tariff is IDR 430 / kg so that the value of rice is obtained before it is processed to rice for IDR. 6,302.5. After being converted to rice with a yield value of 0.65 and processing costs, drying and sacks of IDR. 152.5 / kg, the rice import parity price of IDR. 4,249.1 / kg and added transportation costs to farmers, so import parity prices at farm level of IDR. 4,349.1 / kg.

Table 3. Calculation of Import Parity Price of Rice (Social Price) at Farmer Level

No.	Items	Value
1.	F.O.B. (\$/ton)	435
2.	Freight Cost (%)	1.53%
3.	Insurance cost (%)	0.1951%
3.	CIF Indonesia (\$/ton)	442.5
4.	Exchange rate (IDR/\$)	12,800
5.	Exchange rate premium (%)	0
6.	Equilibrium exchange rate (IDR/\$)	12,800
7.	CIF Indonesian at domestic price (IDR/ton)	5,664,000
8.	Factor of weight conversion (kg/ton)	1,000
9.	CIF Indonesian at domestic price (IDR/kg)	5,664
10.	Port handling	38.5
10.	Cost of handling and transportation to wholesaler (IDR/kg)	170
11.	Cost of import tariff (5%)	430
11.	Value of rice before processing (IDR/kg)	6,302.5
12.	Conversion factor for processing to paddy	0.65
13.	Cost of processing of rice, depreciation, drying, and sack (IDR/kg)	152.5
14.	Import parity price (IDR/kg)	4,249.1
15.	Cost of transportation to farmer (IDR/kg)	100
16.	Import parity price at farmer level (IDR/kg)	4,349.1

Source: Data processed, 2015 year.

2. Input Shadow Price

The shadow price of Urea fertilizer as an export commodity is then used export parity price. The average price of Urea fertilizer export (FOB) according to survey results to PT. Fertilizer Indonesia is US \$ 287 / US \$, with the exchange rate of IDR \$ 13.600 per 1 US \$, the price of CIF Indonesia at the domestic price of IDR 3,903.2 per kg and the cost of port handling (loading and unloading service) for bulk dry commodity IDR 38.5 per kg and transportation costs to wholesalers obtained import parity price IDR 4,117.7 per kg, and after added transportation costs to farmers is obtained import price parity at the farm level IDR 4,269.7 per kg. The cost of freight and insurance is burned by the importing country because it is sold aboard the TanjungPriuk export port (FOB).

Table 4. Calculation of Export Parity Prices of Urea (Europe) at the level Farmers of 2015

No.	Items	Value
1.	F.O.B Indonesia/TanjungPriuk (\$/ton)	287.0
2.	Exchange rate (IDR/\$)	12,800
3.	Exchange rate premium (%)	0
4.	Equilibrium exchange rate (IDR/\$)	12,800
5.	CIF of Indonesia at domestic level (IDR/ton)	3,481,600
6.	Factor of weight conversion (kg/ton)	1,000
7.	CIF of Indonesia at domestic level (IDR/kg)	3,673.6
8.	Port handling	38.5
9.	Custom (tariff of import)	0
10.	Cost of transportation and handling to wholesaler (IDR/kg)	170
11.	Import parity price (IDR/kg)	3,882.1
12.	Cost of transportation to farmer (IDR/kg)	100
13.	Import parity price at farmer level	3,982.1

Source: Primary data, processed, 2015.

Similarly, the export parity price of SP-36 as export goods is used FOB price, with an average price of 341 US \$ per metric ton according to survey results to Indonesian Fertilizer Corporation (Table 5). The method of calculation is the same as the calculation of export parity price of Urea, as shown in Table 5. Export parity price at farmer level according to calculation result is IDR 5,004,1 per kg.

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Table 5. Calculation of Export Parity Price of SP-36 (Europe) at farmer Level in 2015

No.	Items	Value
1.	F.O.B of Indonesian/Tanjungpriuk (\$/ton)	341.0
2.	Exchange rate (IDR/\$)	12,800
3.	Exchange rate premium (%)	0
4.	Equilibrium exchange rate (IDR/\$)	12,800
5.	F.O.B Indonesia at Domestic Price (IDR/ton)	4,364,800
6.	Factor of weight conversion (kg/ton)	1,000
7.	F.O.B Indonesia at Domestic Price (IDR/kg)	4,364.8
8.	Port handling	38.5
9.	Custom (import tarif)	0
10.	Cost of handling and transportation to wholesalers (IDR/kg)	170
11.	Price of Import Parity (IDR/kg)	4,852.1
12.	Transportation Cost to famers (IDR/kg)	100
13.	Price of Import Parity at Famers level	4,673.3

Source: Processed primary data, 2015.

The determination or calculation of the export parity price of NPK fertilizer is also the same as the previous two fertilizers. The details are listed in Table 6. From the calculation result obtained parity price of NPK fertilizer export at farmer level IDR 4,684,5 / kg.

Table 5. Calculation of Export Parity Price of NPK (Europe) at Farmer Level in 2015

No.	Items	Value
1.	F.O.B Indonesia/Tanjungpriuk (\$/ton)	317,5
4.	Exchange rate (IDR/\$)	12,800
5.	Exchange rate premium (%)	0
6.	Equilibrium exchange rate (IDR/\$)	12,800
7.	FOB Indonesia pdHarga domestic (IDR/ton)	4,064,000
8.	Factor of weight conversion (kg/ton)	1,000
9.	F.O.B Indonesia at Domestic Price (IDR/kg)	4,064.0
10.	Port handling	38.5
11.	Custom (import tariff)	0
12.	Cost of handling and transportation to wholesalers (IDR/kg)	170
13.	Price of Import Parity (IDR/kg)	4,272.5
14.	Transportation Cost to famers (IDR/kg)	100
15.	Price of Import Parity at Famers level	4,372.5

Source: Processed primary data, 2015.

Analysis of Rice Competitiveness in Banten Province

Table 6. Table Input – Output Tradable Goods dan Non Tradable Goods Rice Farming on RS 2014/2015 in Banten Province

Type of Input-Output Goods	Non Tradable Goods	Volume	Price (IDR)/Unit		Value of Input-Output (Rp)	
			Financial	Social	Financial	Social
	Seed (kg)					
	a. labeled	25	8318	10000	207950	250000
	b. non labeled	10	2996	2996	29960	29960
Fertilizer (kg):						
	a. Urea	236	1561	3982.1	368396	939776
	b. SP-36	86	1343	4763.3	115498	409644
	c. KCL	5	760	5400	3800	27000
	d. ZA	1.5	2375	3400	3563	5100
	e. NPK Ponska	159	1967	4372.5	312753	695228
	f. Manure fertilizer	52	355	355	18460	18460
	g. Organic Fertilizer(s)	255	497	1500	126735	382500
	h. Liquid Organic Fertilizer (l)	0.2	41875	41875	8375	8375
	i. Solid Fertilizer (kg)	0.3	19110	19110	5733	5733
	j. Liquid Fertilizer (l)	0.7	76541	76541	53579	53579
	Liquid Growing Stimulants (l)	1.1	8199	8199	9019	9019
Pesticide:						
	a. Solid (kg)	7.7	12536	12536	96527	96527
	b. Liquid (l)	2.4	56046	56046	134510	134510
Herbicide:						
	a. Solid (kg)	0.05	168841	168841	8442	8442
	b. Liquid (l)	0.7	65339	65339	45737	45737
	a. Tax of building and land				31937	31937
	b. Contribution of irrigation water free				5348	5348
	c. Contribution of village				1142	1142

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Type of Input-Output Goods	Non Tradable Goods	Volume	Price (IDR)/Unit		Value of Input-Output (Rp)	
			Financial	Social	Financial	Social
Cost of Hired Labour:						
	a. Hired labour (Man Day Work)	100	46616.0	46616	4661598	4661598
	b. Family Labour (MDW)	12	0			0
	c. Hire of Livestock Service	0.1	65000	65000	6500	6500
	d. Hire of Tractor Service	2.6	275496.2	275496	716290	716290
Total Cost					7144591	8715143
Revenue		5835	3725	4349.1	21735375	25376999
Income					14590784	16661855
R/C					3.0	2.9
B/C					2.0	1.9

Source: Primary data processed, 2015 year. Explanation : n = 120 respondents.

Based on the above, the Table of Input-Output of rice farming based on tradable goods (international tradable goods and non tradable goods) can be arranged. Based on the Table 6, the B / C ratio is based on based on the social price is 1.9 meaning that the rice farming is profitable financially and socially (without any market distortion from the government).

Policy Analysis Matrix of Rice Farming

From Table 7 can be compiled matrix analysis policy (policy analysis matrix) as presented in Table 8.

Table 8. Policy analysis matrix of rice farming on RS 2014/2015 in Banten Province

Revenue	Tradable Inputs	Domestic Inputs	Profit
A	B	C	D
Financial	Financial	Financial	Financial
21,735,375	1,180,014	5,679,185	14,876,176
E	F	G	H
Social	Social	Social	Social
25,376,999	2,555,667	5,893,974	16,927,358
Divergences			
-3,641,624	-1,528,502	-155,350	-2,051,182

Remarks: A = Financial revenue. B = Tradable (internationally tradable) input costs in private prices. C = Domestic factor costs in private prices. D = Financial profit. E = Revenue in social prices. F = Tradable input costs in social prices. G = Domestic factor costs in social prices. H = Profit in social price.

Source: Processed primary data, 2015.

From the calculation result of PAM analysis known that the value of PCR (Public Cost Ratio) or Private Ratio 0.28 means that rice commodity has competitive advantage, so to produce one unit of production at financial or private price required 0.28 cost of domestic financial input Table 9).

Table 9. Calculation Result of PAM for Parameter Analyzed

No.	Parameters	Formulation	Value
1.	Competitiveness:		
	a. PCR	$C/(A-B)$	0.28
	b. DRCR	$G/(E - F)$	0.26
2.	Profit Analysis:		
	a. Private Profitability (PP)	$D = A - (B+C)$	14,876,176
		$H = E - (F + G)$	16,927,358
	b. Social Profitability (SP)		
3.	Output Policy:		
	a. Output Transfer (OT)	$A - E$	-3,641,624
	b. NPCO	A/E	0.84
4.	Input Policy:		
	a. Input Transfer (IT)	$B - F$	-1,528,502
	b. NPCI	B/F	0.46

Source: Processed primary data, 2015.

The value of DRCR (Domestic Resources Cost Ratio) is 0.26, which means that rice farming has a comparative advantage, to produce one unit of production at a social price requires only 0.26 cost of domestic resources at social prices. The smaller the value of both the higher the amount of competitiveness. Based on study of Jakiyahet *al.* (2016), that organic red rice, organic black rice, and organic white rice in West Java Province have PCR consecutively of 0.86, 0.79 and 0.88, while the value DRC of 0.66, 0.75, 0.96 consecutively. It is mean that organic rice in West Java has low competitiveness (0.67 – 1.0). Also based on study of Mantauet *al.* (2014) in North Sulawesi province about rice farming competitiveness, they found the value of DRCR is 0.68 and PCR is 0.69, it is mean that rice farming has comparative and competitive advantage, but the value of competitiveness is low (0.67 – 1.0). Also based on study of Rohman (2008) in West Java Province, it was found that Pandan Wangi (Local leading Variety) and New leading Variety rice farming has DRCR value is 0.29 and 0.55 and the value of PCR consecutively 0.7 and 0.9. It is mean that both variety have comparative and competitive advantage with low competitiveness.

Compare to the other countries, such as study of Ogbet *al.* (2011) in Nigeria, which found value of PCR and DRC in irrigated rice land of 0.2353 and 0.0861, respectively. This mean that rice farming in Nigeria has higher competitiveness than Indonesia. Kanaka and Chinnadurai (2013) made study in Tamil Nadu India about competitiveness of rice, and found that value of DRC from 2009 – 2010 is 0.45, is lower competitiveness compare to rice in Banten-Indonesia (0.26).

Based on the profit analysis, it is known that rice commodities provide profit on the financial cost (Private Profitability/ PP) of IDR 14,876,176per ha, and profit based on social price (Social Profitability/SP) of IDR 16,927,358, meaning either with or without Government intervention on the market of rice commodities can provide profit.

Based on the analysis of output policy, obtained value of Output Transfer (OT) of IDR -3,641,624, meaning that there is no subsidy on the output of rice from the government to producers/farmers. This is supported by other parameters is NPCO (Nominal Protection Coefficient on Output) of 0.84 value, that is because NPCO <1, it means that rice farmers do not accept protective policy from government (no subsidy output).

Sensitivity analysis that aims to regard the results of an economic activity analysis if there is a change in the calculation of costs or benefits. This study uses two simulations with, assumption of input changes are: 1) Increase in tradable input prices by 10%, 2)Decrease in output (paddy) prices 10%. The simulation results are listed in Table 10.

Table 10. Analysis of Sensitivity with assumption Input Tradable Price Increase 10% and Paddy Price Decrease 10%

Indicators	Initial Value	Input tradable price increase 10%	Increase/ Decrease (%)	Decrease of paddy prices 10%	Increase/ Decrease (%)
PCR	0.2860	0.2864	0.15	0.3182	10.13
DRCR	0.261	0.258	-1.30	0.258	-1.30
PP	14,261,999	14,393,112	0.91	12,263,337	-16.30
SP	16,657,395	5,879,974	-183.29	5,879,974	0
OT	-4,079,249	-4,079,249	0.00	-6,209,024	34.30
NPCO	0.84	0.84	0.00	0.76	-11.11
IT	-1,528,502	-1,375,652	-11.11	-1,375,652	0
NPCI	0.46	0.46	0	0.46	0

Source: Processed primary data, 2015.

From Table 10, the 10% tradable input price increase will raise the value of competitive advantage (PCR) by 0.15%or decrease the competitive

competitiveness value by 0.15%. In the contrary, the value of comparative advantage (DRCR) is decrease of 1.3% or increase the comparative competitiveness. Private Profitability rose by a very small of 0.91% while social profit fell sharply by 183.3%. Transfer Output has not changed because both financial prices and the amount of output have not changed. Likewise the Output Coefficient Protection Value does not change because only tradable inputs are changed. Meanwhile Input Transfers decreased 11.11%, indicating transfers from tradable input producers (fertilizers, medicines) declined due to increased tradable input prices. For Input Coefficient Protection Values (NPCI) does not change because the increase in input prices for financial and social tradables is comparable.

Simulation with 10% increase of paddy price, result the value of PCR will increase 10.13% or become 0.3182, it is mean that value of competitive competitiveness is decreased. While the value of DRCR will decrease 1.3% become 0.258, and it is mean the value of comparative competitiveness is increase. Private Profitable decrease by 16.30% due to decrease of revenue while Social Price has no changed because only private price of paddy that changed.

Output transfers increased by 34.3%, meaning there was an increase in transfers from producers to the public, while the NPCO value decreased by 11.11%, meaning that the policy of reducing the selling price of 10% soybeans was increasingly disincentive to producers.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The available area of arable land of rice farming in the rainy season 2014/2015 is 0.32 ha, with dominant varieties of Ciherang, Mekongga, IR-64, and Inpari. Average productivity of 5.835 tons per ha. Value of private and social B/C ratio 2.0 and 1.9 respectively, that mean profitable rice farming financially and socially.
1. 2. The value of PCR (Public Cost Ratio) and DRCR (Domestic Resources Cost Ratio) are 0.28 and 0.26 respectively. This means rice commodity has a relatively high competitiveness.
2. 3. The increase of 10% tradable input price will increase the PCR value by 0.15% while the value of DRCR will decrease 1.3%. The Private Profitable (PP) will increase slightly 0.91% while Social Profitable (SP) will decrease sharply namely 183.3%. The decrease of 10% output price will increase PCR 10.13% and will decrease value of DRCR amount of 1.3%.

POLICY RECOMMENDATION

Suggested it's need to increase rice productivity to improve competitiveness and the purchase of grain by Agency of Logistics Affairs according to Government Purchasing Price.

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